

STRYCHNINE AND BRUCINE. PART V. SOME DERIVATIVES OF DINITROISOSTRYCHNIC ACID.

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Dinitroisostrychnic acid is monobasic in character, and it furnishes methyl, ethyl and propyl esters which give crystalline salts. The methiodide of the methyl ester gives *N*-(*b*)-methyl dinitroisostrychnic butaine and the ethyl ester yields by the action of hydrazine hydrate besides a normal hydrazide, two other products of the composition $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_5, H_2O$ and $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_5, \frac{1}{2}H_2O$.

In Part III of this series dinitrostrychnic acid was prepared by the action of 5% nitric acid on strychnine and this was treated with 1% potassium hydroxide and piperidine in order to obtain an insight into the orientation of the molecule and a definite information regarding the state of combination of the α -carbon atom of the indole nucleus. It seemed that by this treatment dinitrostrychnic acid might suffer hydrolytic fission

between *N*(*a*) and the aromatic nucleus and thus offer a means of determining whether the C atom attached to *N*(*a*) is secondary or tertiary. By the action of aqueous alkali on dinitrostrychnic acid, a product is obtained which is considered for some time to be an isomer of the acid or the salt of the phenol after cleavage had occurred in the molecule. To decide this it was necessary to examine dinitroisostrychnic acid by comparing some of its derivatives with those of dinitrostrychnic acid. The present investigation shows clearly that alkali treatment does not produce an isomer. The methyl, ethyl and propyl esters and their salts are not identical and one interesting thing in the melting points of the esters is observed. The melting points of the esters of dinitrostrychnic acid rise from methyl, ethyl to propyl, while the m. p. of the isomer goes down likewise as the following table shows.

Esters of dinitrostrychnic acid.			Esters of dinitroisostrychnic acid.		
		m.p.			m.p.
Methyl ester	...	210-211°	Methyl ester	...	225°
Ethyl ester	...	226°	Ethyl ester	...	195°
Propyl ester	...	246°	Propyl ester	...	118-22°

The action of hydrazine hydrate also differs on the two acids. In the case of dinitrostrychnic acid normal hydrazide is obtained, while the isomer gives besides a normal hydrazide, two other products of the composition $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_5 \cdot H_2O$ (m.p. 221°) and $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_5 \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ (m.p. 161°). The action of piperidine on ethyl ester does not produce any change and the ester is recovered quantitatively, while nitrous acid gives only a nitrite. The methyl ester follows the normal course in giving N(b)-methyl dinitrostrychnic-betaine *via* methiodide and chloride. All the esters and their derivatives give well defined crystalline salts.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl Dinitroisostrychnate.—A mixture of dinitroisostrychnic acid nitrate (2 g.), prepared as mentioned in part IV of this series, methyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2.5 c.c.) was kept gently simmering over a free flame for 7 hours when the substance gradually dissolved to an orange-red solution and was then boiled down to 8 c.c. On adding a few drops of acetic acid methyl dinitroisostrychnate crystallised in long needles. Its acetic acid solution on basification with sodium carbonate (the brownish yellow impurities neglected) gave a bright yellow precipitate which was dissolved in chloroform. The solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to 5 c.c. On adding methyl alcohol to the solution methyl dinitroisostrychnate was obtained in dull yellow prisms. It dissolves readily in chloroform, sparingly in methyl and ethyl alcohol and is insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. It crystallised from ethyl acetate, benzene and acetone in prisms, m.p. 225° (softening at 218°). On drying in *vacuo* at 100° it suffers no loss in weight and shows the presence of one methoxyl group. (Found in anhydrous material: C, 57.5, 57.5; H, 5.3, 5.4; N, 12.1, 12.0; OMe, 8.0. $C_{22}H_{24}O_7N_4$ requires C, 57.9; H, 5.3; N, 12.3; OMe, 7.0 per cent).

The *sulphate* (needles) dissolves in hot water and sparingly in ethanol. It chars at 280-90°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 47.0; H, 5.4; OMe, 4.0. $C_{22}H_{24}O_7N_4 \cdot H_2SO_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 46.7; H, 5.0; OMe 5.5 per cent).

The *hydrochloride*, obtained as long prisms by adding hydrogen chloride in ether to a chloroform solution of the base, is soluble in methanol. It chars at 225-35° (softening at 194°). (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: Cl, 6.5. $C_{22}H_{24}O_7N_4 \cdot HCl$ requires Cl, 7.2 per cent).

The *picrate*, obtained as a bright yellow flocculent mass by adding ethereal picric acid to a chloroform solution of the base, turns into a bright yellow powder on boiling with methanol. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and water, m.p. 259° (decomp.).

The *methiodide*.—To methyl dinitroisostrychnate (0.5 g.), dissolved in dry chloroform (15 c.c.), methyl iodide (0.5 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was added and from the clear orange-red solution a sticky reddish product separated. The reactants were left well corked overnight at room temperature when the mass crystallised in thin needles. After adding ether the crystalline methiodide was collected and washed with chloroform and ether. It is soluble in ethanol and water, m.p. 276-80° (decomp.). After drying at 100° in *vacuo* it suffered no loss in weight, and showed the presence of one methoxyl and one *N*-methyl group. (Found in anhydrous material: C, 46.4; H, 4.9; N, 9.3; OMe, 5.0; NMe, 4.8; I, 21.1. $C_{22}H_{24}O_7N_4 \cdot MeI$ requires C, 46.2; H, 4.5; N, 9.4; OMe, 5.2; NMe, 4.8; I, 21.2 per cent).

N(b)-Methyl Dinitroisostrychnic Betaine.—An aqueous solution of the methiodide, when treated with freshly precipitated silver oxide, turned red. The filtered solution on concentration turned yellow and deposited thin needles of the betaine which were collected and washed with a little water and alcohol. It is soluble in hot water but insoluble in ethanol and other common organic solvents and does not melt below 325°. It showed the presence of one *N*-methyl group and was free from methoxyl group. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 55.0; H, 5.2; N, 11.0; NMe, 5.8. $C_{22}H_{25}O_7N_4 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 54.5; H, 5.8; N, 11.6; NMe, 6.0 per cent).

The *picrate*, prepared in aqueous solution as pale yellow mass, turns into closely packed bunches of needles on rubbing with methanol. It is soluble in warm alcohol and water and gradually decomposes at 259°.

Ethyl Dinitroisostrychnate.—Dinitroisostrychnic acid was esterified with 5% ethyl alcoholic sulphuric acid. Addition of ether deposited ethyl dinitroisostrychnate sulphate in short stout prisms. A further yield was obtained from the filtrate after removal of the solvent. The sulphate was

converted into ethyl ester base and its chloroform solution on concentration and addition of ethanol precipitated the ester in cubes. It also crystallises from ethyl acetate, acetone, benzene and ethanol in prisms and is insoluble in ether and petroleum ether, m.p. 195° (softening at 192°). After drying at 100° it was analysed and showed the presence of one OEt group. [Found: C, 58.1; H, 6.1; N, 11.5; OEt, 11.0. $C_{23}H_{26}O_7N_4$ requires C, 58.7; H, 5.5; N, 11.9; OEt (for 1), 12.1 per cent].

The *sulphate* is easily soluble in water and dissolves sparingly in ethanol. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in prisms which decomposed at 250° (frothing at 150°).

The *hydrochloride*, obtained in prismatic plates by adding ethereal hydrogen chloride to a chloroform solution of the base, is soluble in alcohol and water and gradually decomposes at 247° .

The *picrate*, prepared in ether-chloroform solution as bright yellow flocculent mass, on washing with a little chloroform and methanol turned into pale yellow needles, soluble in alcohol and water, m. p. 261° (decomp).

Action of Piperidine on Ethyl Dinitroisostychnate.—Ethyl dinitroisostychnate (0.6 g.) was refluxed in dry dioxan (60 c.c.) with piperidine (1 g.) for 4 hours. The red solution on dilution with water gave a flocculant precipitate (0.5 g.) which on recrystallisation had m.p. $153-55^{\circ}$. The filtrate further gave a crystalline product (0.05 g.), m.p. 168° , but neither of the two fractions gave any depression with the original substance, and thus they appear to be its hydrates.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Ethyl Dinitroisostychnate.—To ethyl dinitroisostychnate (0.6 g.), dissolved in hydrochloric acid (15 c.c., 10%), a solution of sodium nitrite in a few drops of water was added with ice cooling and shaking. On leaving the mixture well corked overnight the nitrite of the ester separated in lemon-yellow needles which on recrystallisation melted at $198-99^{\circ}$. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: N, 11.68. $C_{22}H_{26}O_7N_4, HNO_2, H_2O$ requires N, 13.1 per cent). The base from this crystallised in rectangular plates and frothed up at $154-55^{\circ}$. The mixture with the original substance also frothed up at the same temperature. The base was the hydrated form and showed the presence of 1 OEt group. (Found in an undried sample: C, 56.2; H, 5.6; N, 11.3; OEt, 8.0. $C_{23}H_{26}O_7N_4, H_2O$ requires C, 56.6; H, 5.7; N, 11.5; OEt, 9.2 per cent).

Bromination of Ethyl Dinitroisostychnate.—The ethyl ester (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry chloroform (10 c.c.) and to this bromine (0.2 g.) in chloroform (3 c.c.) was added dropwise under ice cooling. On adding ether to the solution a yellow substance separated which crystallised from

methanol-ether mixture in hexagonal prisms, m.p. 200-1°. (Found in an undried sample: Br, 16.6. Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 47.2; H, 5.1; N, 9.6; Br, 16.6. $C_{23}H_{26}O_7N_4Br \cdot 2H_2O$ requires C, 47.2; H, 5.0; N, 9.6; Br, 13.7 per cent). It was macerated with ammonia and its solution in chloroform after washing and drying gave a sticky residue which could not be induced to crystallise and was, therefore, precipitated with ether in acetone solution. The powder so obtained was soluble in alcohol, acetone and chloroform and gradually melted at 180°. (Found in an undried sample: C, 50.4; H, 5.2; N, 9.0; Br, 14.5; OEt, 9.2. $C_{23}H_{25}O_7N_4Br$ requires C, 50.3; H, 4.5; N, 10.2; Br, 14.6 OEt, 9.6 per cent).

Action of Hydrazine Hydrate on Ethyl Dinitroisostrychnate.—Ethyl dinitroisostrychnate (4 g.) was dissolved in butyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and on adding hydrazine hydrate (7 g.) the orange solution turned red. It was refluxed for 45 minutes, when a solid separated after 15 minutes. It was allowed to cool and the crystalline mass collected (3 g.). A further yield (0.5 g.) was obtained on adding acetone to the concentrated solution. The combined crystalline solid was dissolved in methanol when a portion remained undissolved (A). The alcohol-soluble fraction gave a further small yield of (A) besides a crystalline solid which could be separated into acetone-insoluble (B) and acetone-soluble (C) fractions.

Fraction (A): Dinitroisostrychnic Hydrazide.—It was dissolved in methanol under reflux and from the solution on cooling the hydrazide separated as a crystalline mass, insoluble in acetone, benzene, ethyl acetate, ether and chloroform and did not melt below 280° and showed the absence of ethoxyl group. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 54.7; H, 5.7; N, 17.5. $C_{21}H_{21}O_6N_4 \cdot NH \cdot NH_2, \frac{1}{4}H_2O$ requires C, 54.8; H, 5.4; N, 18.1 per cent).

Fraction B—This was easily soluble in cold methanol and on adding acetone crystallised in prisms, insoluble in ethyl acetate and benzene and frothed up at 221° (loss at 100°, 7.6%; $2H_2O$ requires 7.84 per cent). (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 53.50, 53.4; H, 5.7, 5.7; N, 15.5. $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_5, H_2O$ requires C, 54.9; H, 5.5; N, 15.3 per cent). The *picrate* was obtained in glistening plates, m.p. 225-35° (frothing).

Fraction C.—This was crystallised from methanol in prisms, soluble in chloroform, ethyl acetate, benzene and frothed up at 160°. It was free from ethoxyl group and after drying at 100° in *vacuo* lost 4.5% H_2O (theory requires 4.2%). (Found in dried material: C, 57.2; H, 5.7; N, 17.4. $C_{21}H_{23}O_6N_5, \frac{1}{4}H_2O$ requires C, 57.5; H, 5.6; N, 16.8 per cent). The *picrate*, prepared in methanol-ether solution, melted at 225-35° (decomp.) (frothing at 178°).

Propyl Dinitroisostrychnate.—Propyl dinitroisostrychnate was also prepared in a similar fashion; the base crystallised on the addition of propyl alcohol to its chloroform solution as prismatic needles, m.p. 118-22°. After drying in *vacuo* at 100° it suffered no loss in weight. (Found: C, 58.0; H, 6.5; N, 11.3. $C_{24}H_{28}O_7N_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 58.4; H, 5.9; N, 11.4 per cent).

The *sulphate* was sparingly soluble in water and alcohol and was recrystallised from the former in needles, m.p. 247-48° (decomp.). The *hydrochloride*, prepared in chloroform-ether solution as a sticky mass, crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 225° (frothing) and was sparingly soluble in water. The *picrate*, obtained as a pale yellow powder, was very sparingly soluble in alcohol and water and had m.p. 241-44° (decomp.)

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Professor Sir Robert Robinson, Kt., F.R.S. for his advice and encouragement throughout this investigation and to the Trustees, Dawoodbhoy Fazalbhoy Muslim Educational Trust, Bombay, for the grant of an educational loan which enabled the author to take part in this work.

The micro-analyses were done by Drs. Weiller, Strauss and Miss Martin.

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Received December 24, 1939.
